

Supplementary Material for Bringing Automation to Electromagnetic: Robotic Scanning of Magnetic Field in Electric Drives

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S.I. MEASUREMENT ERROR ANALYSIS

The accuracy of the Hall-effect sensor measurement is influenced by multiple independent error sources, including sensor linearity deviation, temperature-induced drift, quantization of analog-to-digital conversion (ADC) and mechanical positioning uncertainty. Each of these factors contributes to the overall uncertainty and their combined effect is estimated using the root sum of squares (RSS) method. The key parameters used in the error analysis are summarized in Table I.

The sensor output voltage is given by:

$$V_{\text{out}} = S \times B \quad (1)$$

where S is the sensitivity (in mV/mT) and B is the applied magnetic field (in mT). Using the datasheet values:

$$V_{\text{out, min}} = 10 \times 65 = 650 \text{ mV} \quad (2)$$

$$V_{\text{out, typ}} = 14 \times 100 = 1400 \text{ mV} \quad (3)$$

$$V_{\text{out, max}} = 17.5 \times 100 = 1750 \text{ mV} \quad (4)$$

Error Contributions

(1) Linearity Error: The datasheet specifies a linearity deviation (E_{lin}) of $\pm 0.7\%$ of the span:

$$\Delta V_{\text{linearity}} = 0.007 \times V_{\text{out}} \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta V_{\text{linearity, min}} = 0.007 \times 650 = \pm 4.55 \text{ mV} \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta V_{\text{linearity, typ}} = 0.007 \times 1400 = \pm 9.8 \text{ mV} \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta V_{\text{linearity, max}} = 0.007 \times 1750 = \pm 12.25 \text{ mV} \quad (8)$$

(2) Temperature Drift Error: Sensitivity drift is given as $\pm 0.15\%$ per $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Over a temperature change of $\Delta T = 60^{\circ}\text{C}$:

$$\Delta V_{\text{temp}} = 0.0015 \times V_{\text{out}} \times 60 \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta V_{\text{temp, min}} = 0.0015 \times 650 \times 60 = \pm 58.5 \text{ mV} \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta V_{\text{temp, typ}} = 0.0015 \times 1400 \times 60 = \pm 126 \text{ mV} \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta V_{\text{temp, max}} = 0.0015 \times 1750 \times 60 = \pm 157.5 \text{ mV} \quad (12)$$

(3) ADC Quantization Error: The 14-bit ADC with input range ± 10 V introduces a quantization step of:

$$Q = \frac{20 \text{ V}}{2^{14}} = 1.22 \text{ mV} \quad (13)$$

Since the ADC error is ± 1 LSB, we have:

$$\Delta V_{\text{ADC}} = \pm 1.22 \text{ mV} \quad (14)$$

Since these errors are independent, the total uncertainty is determined using the root sum of squares (RSS) method:

$$\Delta V_{\text{total}} = \sqrt{(\Delta V_{\text{linearity}})^2 + (\Delta V_{\text{temp}})^2 + (\Delta V_{\text{ADC}})^2} \quad (15)$$

(1) Minimum Case (650 mV Output)

$$\Delta V_{\text{total, min}} = \sqrt{(4.55)^2 + (58.5)^2 + (1.22)^2} = \pm 58.7 \text{ mV} \quad (16)$$

(2) Typical Case (1400 mV Output)

$$\Delta V_{\text{total, typ}} = \sqrt{(9.8)^2 + (126)^2 + (1.22)^2} = \pm 126.4 \text{ mV} \quad (17)$$

(3) Maximum Case (1750 mV Output)

$$\Delta V_{\text{total, max}} = \sqrt{(12.25)^2 + (157.5)^2 + (1.22)^2} = \pm 157.9 \text{ mV} \quad (18)$$

Thus, the total uncertainty in the Hall sensor measurement varies between ± 58.7 mV (± 1.95 mT) and ± 157.9 mV (± 5.26 mT). The typical measurement error, calculated using the nominal sensor output voltage of 1400 mV, is ± 126.4 mV (± 4.21 mT). Temperature drift remains the dominant contributor to the total error, followed by the linearity deviation.

TABLE I
EXTRACTED KEY VALUES FROM THE DATASHEET

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Units
Supply Voltage	V_s	5.0	V
Sensitivity (Min/Typ/Max)	$S_{\text{min}}, S_{\text{typ}}, S_{\text{max}}$	10 / 14 / 175	mV/mT
Linearity Error	E_{lin}	$\pm 0.7\%$	% of span
Temperature Drift of Sensitivity	E_{temp}	$\pm 0.15\%$	% per $^{\circ}\text{C}$
Temperature Range	ΔT	60 (e.g., 25°C to 85°C)	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
Magnetic Field Range (Min/Typ)	$B_{\text{min}}, B_{\text{typ}}$	$\pm 65 / \pm 100$	mT
ADC Resolution	N	14	Bits
ADC Input Range	$V_{\text{ADC, range}}$	± 10	V

S.II. POSTPROCESSING TRANSFORMATIONS OF MAGNETIC FIELD COMPONENTS FROM TCP TO LOCAL SENSOR FRAMES

In a three-Hall sensor probe, each sensor measures only one component of the magnetic field along a dedicated axis. These sensors are displaced in three dimensions from the Tool Center Point (TCP), which requires a transformation to obtain the correct local measurements.

Let the TCP be represented as:

$$\mathbf{r}_{TCP} = [x_{TCP}, y_{TCP}, z_{TCP}]^T. \quad (19)$$

Each Hall sensor is positioned at a displacement \mathbf{d}_i from the TCP, given by:

$$\mathbf{r}_i = \mathbf{r}_{TCP} + \mathbf{d}_i, \quad (20)$$

where the displacement vector for each sensor is:

$$\mathbf{d}_i = [d_{x,i}, d_{y,i}, d_{z,i}]^T. \quad (21)$$